

FEATURES OF SUICIDAL BEHAVIOR IN PATIENTS OF GERONTOPSYCHIATRIC
DEPARTMENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10613546>

Abstract. *To date, the suicide movement is an important world-class problem of medical and socio-economic importance. The sexual and age characteristics of suicide are important factors in the distribution of suicide attempts, not just suicide.*

Key words: *gerontopsychiatry, suicide, psychiatric care, nosological form.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ СУИЦИДАЛЬНОГО ПОВЕДЕНИЯ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ
ГЕРОНТОПСИХИАТРИЧЕСКИХ ОТДЕЛЕНИЙ

Аннотация. *На сегодняшний день суицидальное движение представляет собой важную проблему мирового уровня, имеющую медицинское и социально-экономическое значение. Половые и возрастные особенности суицида являются важными факторами распределения суицидальных попыток, а не только суицида.*

Ключевые слова: *геронтопсихиатрия, суицид, психиатрическая помощь, нозологическая форма.*

Introduction. Suicide is one of the most important health problems in most countries of the world. According to the WHO, more than one million people commit suicide each year. In recent decades, our country has been characterized by high rates of death due to suicide, more than 20 cases per 100 thousand residents. According to the most severe forms of suicide behavior and patients with a high risk of suicide, specialized psychiatric care should be provided in a 24-hour hospital. Often, treatment is carried out with the help of mandatory restrictive measures, in which the patient directly threatens the safety of his life and others [1-5]. Treatment aimed at eliminating psychopathological symptoms should lead to an improvement in the mental state of patients and

neutralization of suicidal thoughts. However, patients at high risk of suicide may attempt suicide in the hospital, on treatment Leave, or in the early stages after discharge [6-9].

Throughout the history of the development of psychiatric care, there has been a gradual improvement in the quality of life of patients, which has led to a reduction in the risk of suicide behaviors and, ultimately, a decrease in mortality in psychiatric hospitals. If in the 9th century. the functions of psychiatric institutions were reduced to seeing the mentally ill, then in the first half of the 20th century. active methods of treatment and diagnosis of mental disorders, including depressive disorders, have already appeared, a system of inpatient and non-inpatient forms of psychiatric care has been created [10-16]. Therefore, unlike the situation in the VIII-IX centuries, the mortality rate in psychiatric hospitals is much lower, but suicide continues among them [17-19].

Cases of suicide and attempted suicide in a psychiatric hospital were not recorded in statistical documents, part of the contingent of patients after the suicide attempt died in medical institutions of somatic profile, part was recorded as accidents. Nevertheless, the prevalence rate of suicidal behavior is an important criterion for the quality of psychiatric care provided by the treatment institution [20-23]. For example, according to annual reports, about 10 percent of inpatient suicide was committed by patients from psychiatric clinics, which accounted for 2.5 percent of all suicides in the general population [24]. Trials against psychiatric hospitals in cases of suicide by relatives of suicide victims are common abroad. If one of the four outpatient suicides causes relatives claims, every second case between inpatient suicides leads to a hearing. Courts and juries view stationary units as having a higher level of patient control and thus more responsible for preventing suicide. The incidence of suicide deaths in the United States is important in the licensing of medical organizations by the Joint Commission on Accreditation of health organizations (JCAHO). Suicide in psychiatric hospitals is called " signal events " because they express the need for immediate response and investigation. The terms " Signal event " and " medical error " are not synonymous; not all " signal " events are caused by error, and not all errors need analysis and examination [25-28]. Despite the active development of suicide as a separate area of Psychiatry in Russia and abroad in recent times, not enough attention has been paid to the problem of diagnosing and preventing suicide behavior during treatment in a psychiatric hospital and in the early stages after discharge [29-31].

In the elderly and elderly, the suicide rate is about three times higher than in young people aged 15 to 24 years. This trend is characteristic of both sexes, but is more pronounced in men [32-35].

Late age is accompanied by the loss of loved ones, loss of social status, deterioration of somatic health. Due to the decrease in adaptive abilities, older people find it difficult to adapt to changes in the environment, get lost in the intensive flow of various information, accumulate resentment and misunderstandings about the behavior of young people. The presence of depressive disorders in older people determines suicidal activity with a higher mortality rate. These factors confirm the need for further study of the problem of suicidal behavior in late life [36-40].

The purpose of the study was to improve the provision of psychiatric care to patients at the gerontopsychiatric Hospital who identify suicidal behaviors in various nosological forms of mental pathology.

Materials and methods. 62 patients between the ages of 55 and 75 who were admitted to the Smolensk regional clinical psychiatric hospital were examined. Patient registration was carried out no later than 48 hours after admission, which, in the event of a suicide attempt, coincided with the early postsocial period. Suicide behaviors were evaluated using the suicide reasoning scale (SSI) and the Pierce suicide intent scale (PSIS). The Montgomery-Asberg scale (Mads) and the Beck Depression survey (BDI) have been used to investigate Affective Disorders.

Results and their discussion. As part of the study, the clinical and psychopathological characteristics of internal forms of suicide behavior were studied, the factors and extent of suicide risk were found to be related to the corresponding spectrum of mental disorders. The gerontopsychiatric branch concluded that the psychological portrait of a suicidal person was made taking into account the dynamics of the development of suicidal behavior in the pre - and post-suicidal periods.

An analysis of psychometric scales found the presence of symptoms of anxiety-depressive syndrome. The MADDS score of 20 to 39 accounted for 64,5 percent of suicides, corresponding to clinically significant moderate or severe depression. Objective symptoms of depression were observed in 90.3% and only 54,8 of the respondents% depression is subjective. Nearly half of the respondents had difficulty actively participating. Each second person recorded internal tension and had trouble sleeping, and $\frac{2}{3}$ a contingent of patients occasionally or continuously expressed pessimistic and suicidal thoughts. 58% of patients were found to have anxiety, confirming the predominance of anxiety-depressive symptoms. These data, according to the authors, should be considered depressive, depressive-hypochondriacal, depressive-paranoid and high – risk of suicide-disturbing-depressive. This indicates that Affective Disorders in older suicides primarily need psychopharmacotherapy and psychocorrection, taking into account the features of the structure and course of depression to prevent recurrence of suicidal behavior. Thus, the main

strategy for Suicide Prevention among the elderly is to effectively treat depression using pharmacological and psychological techniques together.

The score of 10 to 25,8 corresponding to the average and high suicide risk on the SSI scale, was 64,5% of suicides. 38.7% of patients experienced a desire to attempt suicide. The beck scale (suicide clause) found that 74,2% of patients had visited suicidal thoughts they did not intend to commit, and 16% wanted to commit suicide. An analysis of the results of Pierce's suicide intention scale showed that more than half (64,5%) of respondents were convinced of the death of the attempted method.

The study of suicide attempt methods found a statically significant ($p < 0,005$) advantage of self-poisoning as a suicide attempt method (fig. 1) and 35.49%. Self-heating and electrical damage are rarely selected (5,9%, respectively). Intermediate positions took over lifesaving techniques such as self-cutting (25,8%), self-discovery (19.3%), and self-scarring in the form of height drops (13%).

The choice of suicide attempt method had gender differences. In half of all cases, women resorted to self-poisoning (50.4%), usually medication.

Men with approximately the same frequency performed self-poisoning (23,4%), self-injection (23,5%) and sapoporesis (29,4%). Falling from a height as a suicide attempt method was chosen by 21,4% of women and only 5,9% of men. Electrical damage and spontaneous floods have only been recorded in men. In general, men chose more brutal and traumatic methods of suicide, which often led to a complex postsocial period and required medical care in a general somatic hospital.

Most suicide attempts occurred in the evening and at night (71%), which is most likely due to increased symptoms of anxiety and depression in the afternoon, Affective Disorders of exogenous organic and vascular nature.

Thus, detailed information about the method of suicide makes it possible to predict the dynamics and severity of the risk of suicide. The reasons for attempted suicide were distributed as follows: protest or retaliation acted as a motive for attempted suicide in 13% of cases, calling or seeking mercy in 35,5%, avoiding suffering or punishment in 9,7%, and giving up life in 32,2% of cases. Both men and women critically evaluated suicide attempts. While half of the cases contain critical and manipulative types of postsuicide, gender analysis of the remaining cases has revealed some differences. In 22,6% of women, a manipulative variant of the postsuicide was observed, which often led to repeated suicide attempts.

During the study, the importance of anxiety-depressive symptoms in suicide was confirmed, the role and severity of depressive disorders were found, and the risk of suicide in the elderly with mental disorders was moderate and increased. Factors affecting the long and chronic development of suicidal behavior have been identified. Typical manifestations of suicide attempt methods and internal forms of suicide behavior are described in the form of suicidal thoughts, plans, and a desire to attempt suicide.

The risk of the appearance, development and recurrence of suicidal behavior, variants of the postsocial period in the elderly mentally ill were analyzed.

Conclusions. The results made it possible to increase the effectiveness of psychiatric profile geriatric units in providing suicide care for elderly patients.

Thus, although elderly suicidal behaviors are equally common in men and women, and independent of habitat, men have a significantly higher risk of suicide. Factors that increase its level include severe somatic pathology and alcohol dependence syndrome. Among the mental pathologies of old age, the most suicidal risk can be called organic mental and Affective Disorders. Of particular importance in the structure of affective disorders are symptoms of depression and anxiety. The latter, a feeling of internal tension and discomfort, combined with an increase in dissomnia, can be the trigger for the transfer of internal forms of suicide to the act of suicide. The increased risk of suicide in elderly mental patients is associated with a higher percentage of suicidal confidence in the death of the suicide method and the desire to attempt suicide. The findings make it possible to improve the prevention and diagnosis of suicide behavior in the age group studied.

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